

Towards a Universal Stanford Dependencies parallel treebank

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Abstract

The paper describes the process conceived to convert a multilingual parallel treebank, namely ParTUT, into an annotated resource that conforms to the representation format and specifications of the Universal Stanford Dependencies (USD).

The main goal of this work is to create, taking an already existing resource as the starting point, a fully parallel treebank that is featured by a widely-known and used representation format, i.e. that of the Stanford Dependencies, and in particular its cross-linguistic variant, namely the Universal Stanford Dependencies, in order to provide a useful resource for a number of NLP tasks, including those that have typically benefitted from such representation format, such as Information Extraction and statistical parsing, but also translation-related tasks (by virtue of the parallel annotation).

1 Introduction

The increasing need to use multilingual resources for NLP systems goes hand in hand with the opportunity to make such resources available and accessible. Nevertheless, the specific morphological and syntactic features of the language at issue, or the end use the resources have been designed for, can motivate the exploitation of different representation formats, thus limiting their accessibility and portability. As for treebanks in particular, a few steps towards the harmonization of datasets and formats that could be easily shared by the community have recently led to the spread of the Stanford Typed Dependencies (SD) [5] as a *de facto* standard, and to its cross-linguistic variant, namely the Universal Stanford Dependencies (USD) [4].

A further step, beyond the development and application of the SD and USD formats in multilingual resources, is the development of *parallel* and possibly aligned data in SD and USD, which could be crucial for translation-related tasks.

This motivates our present work, which consists in the development of a parallel treebank in USD format that could benefit from the annotation scheme and

therefore could be further exploited for translation purposes.

Therefore, the paper describes a project of conversion into USD of an existing parallel treebank for Italian, English and French. In particular, we discuss the challenges encountered in the application of a SD format in a cross-linguistic perspective.

The paper is organized as follows: after a section where the main SD-related formats are reported, we briefly describe the resource to be converted, while Section 4 and 5 are devoted to the description of the approach adopted and to some of the main challenges encountered during conversion.

2 Related Work on Stanford Dependencies

While the SD format has been primarily conceived for English, as also shown by the recently-developed English Web Treebank [15], in the last few years, it has been partly re-designed to be successfully used for other languages, such as Hebrew [16] and Finnish [6], even converting resources that were previously available in other formats, instead of developing new datasets from scratch: this is the case, for example, of the Italian Stanford Dependencies Treebank [1] and the set of six treebanks (English, French, German, Spanish, Swedish and Korean) annotated in basic SD [10].

The success and applicability of the SD standard to practical tasks is also attested by its use in experiments like in NLP contests, such as the shared tasks on Dependency Parsing for Information Extraction (DPIE) and Cross-Language Dependency Parsing (CLaP) at EVALITA 2014¹, the evaluation campaign for Italian NLP tools. However, observing the SD scheme in the perspective of the application to different text types, two main limitations have been detected and reported in [9], i.e. that the scheme does not offer coverage of a large variety of complex syntactic constructions and of constructions typical of informal language.

An attempt to re-build the SD taxonomy in a cross-linguistic perspective is finally proposed with the so-called Universal SD [4], which has also been applied to experiment the "stanfordization" of thirty dependency treebanks in the HamleDT project [12].

As regards the conversion project presented here, our main reference is namely the USD format, and in a similar fashion to most of the conversion projects mentioned above, we do not aim to create a brand new resource using USD as a native representation format, but we rather develop a USD-based parallel resource starting from an already existing one. This is motivated by the need to use a universal annotation standard that could preserve a higher degree of parallelism between the language pairs involved, in order to exploit the parallel annotation for translation purposes.

¹<http://www.evalita.it/>

3 ParTUT and its content

The parallel resource to be converted is ParTUT², a dependency-based treebank of Italian, English and French, developed as the multilingual extension (thus using the same principles and annotation format) of the Turin University Treebank (TUT)³.

The whole treebank currently comprises an overall amount of 148,000 tokens, with approximately 2,200 sentences in the Italian and English sections, and 1,050 sentences for French (being the resource under constant development, the French part of the newest texts recently added to the collection is yet to be analyzed and included).

Although the first release of the resource mostly included parallel texts from the legal domain, its later extensions opened to a larger variety of genres, in order to provide a broader selection of texts for a more efficient training of parsers. As a matter of fact, it has been shown that the performance of parsing systems can be improved by training and testing mixed genres rather than formal and thoroughly revised texts [15]. Bearing this principle in mind, the resource has been recently enriched with fairly different text genres that include web articles from Project Syndicate⁴ and Wikipedia articles retrieved in English and French and then translated into Italian by two teams of graduate students in Translation.

ParTUT consists of human-checked sentences analyzed using the Turin University Linguistic Environment (TULE) [8], a rule-based parser first developed for Italian and then adapted for English and French.

One of the main uses of the treebank is the creation of a system for the automatic alignment of parallel sentences taking into account the syntactic information provided by annotation [14].

4 Converting ParTUT: a rule-based approach

Differences among formats mainly deal with the type of relations, their granularity, and the different notions of specific phenomena assumed in the representation, such as coordination, subordinate clauses, verb groups; these were the aspects we mainly focused on while designing the conversion process.

We conceived our approach to conversion in a similar fashion to Rosa et al. for HamleDT [12], attempting to adhere as much as possible to the original USD core scheme and label set. However, contrarily to HamleDT, where most of the adaptation concerned the label set only, the conversion process from TUT also entailed a partial or complete reshaping of subtrees. We thus identified three classes of relations, according to the way they had to be treated:

- R-renamed: most of the relations had to be simply renamed, as they represent the same grammatical function and link the same elements in both formats;

²<http://www.di.unito.it/~tutreeb/partut.html>

³<http://www.di.unito.it/~tutreeb/>, around 3,500 Italian sentences and 102,000 tokens.

⁴<http://www.project-syndicate.org/>

e.g. VERB-RMOD+RELCL⁵, that is the relation linking the head node of a relative clause to the rest of the sentence, is renamed *relcl*, and PDET-RMOD, which links predeterminers with determiners, is renamed *predet*.

- R-swapped: besides the renaming, the conversion of these relations involves the direct swapping between governor and dependent. This class includes, in particular, the relation linking determiner with noun and preposition with its argument; TUT in fact follows the tenets of the Word Grammar [7], where determiners and prepositions are complementizers of content words, while in SD content words are usually considered as heads of the structure where they occur. Also the relation linking the modal with the main verb, and the one linking the predicative complement to the copula (see Figure 1) are in this class.

Figure 1: An example of copulative verb in TUT format (on the left) and its conversion into USD (on the right).

- R-reshaped: relations whose conversion consists in a full reshaping of the structure where they occur. This class includes, for example, elliptical structures, where the elided material is usually preserved in the TUT representation by means of co-indexed traces, while USD scheme replicates the representation pattern from Lexical Functional Grammar [2], adopting the *remnant* relation (see Figure 2⁶).

Figure 2: Elliptical structure in TUT format (on the left) and its conversion into USD (on the right).

⁵According to the usual notation of TUT and SD, the relations names are in capital letters and in italics respectively.

⁶For the sake of readability, we just retained the more relevant labels.

Comparing TUT and SD format, different granularities of relations often occur (see also 5). The former has been designed in principle for a detailed representation of morphologically rich languages and also exploits null elements in order to generate a full description of the predicate argument structure. The latter aims to provide a simple and intuitive way of annotating dependencies [9]. Different granularities of relations are treated during conversion in two ways: when SD is less specific than TUT, which is the more frequent situation, two or more TUT relations are labeled with a same SD relation, while when TUT is less specific than SD, we constrain the conversion of the single TUT relation with conditions that allow the selection of two or more different relations in SD. For instance, the relation linking the determiner with the noun, i.e. DET-ARG in TUT, is converted in *det* when the determiner is an article and *poss* when it is a possessive adjective.

Furthermore, the implemented conversion includes preprocessing steps for the adaptation of the notation and the conversion of the Part-of-Speech tagset. The adaptation step basically deals with the shift from the word-centered notation of the TUT format⁷ to the USD notation, which is (in compliance with basic SD) centered upon relations.

As regards the PoS tagset, according to the parameters set in the conversion, it can be currently maintained in the native TUT, although we are also developing the conversion into the tagset proposed in the USD guidelines⁸, which is an extended version of the Google universal tagset [11].

Finally, the resource will be also released in the revised CoNLL-U format⁹.

Following the relation taxonomy used by the authors in the provided documentation (see previous footnotes), Figure 3 summarizes how the main TUT relations are mapped onto the USD scheme. The '(...)' sign that surrounds some of the relations in the TUT column represents the possible morpho-syntactic specifications of the relations.

4.1 Mapping functions

Each mapping function is structured according to the following pattern:

```
TUTrelation,SDrelation(Xfeaturetype:condition)
```

where `TUTrelation` is namely the relation to be converted and `SDrelation` is its counterpart, the `X` stands for the element (`G` = governor, `D` = dependent) and the `featuretype` for the feature (`mor` and `syn` for morphological and syntactical features respectively) to which the condition is applied, while `condition` represents a condition that can be required for the relation mapping.

If the slot contains one (or more) condition, it should then be verified on the appropriate element (`G` or `D`) and/or feature (`mor` or `syn`):

⁷Each TUT annotation line includes a word `W`, its PoS tag and the morphological features, the link to the governing node and the relation that labels that link.

⁸<http://universaldependencies.github.io/docs/ud-pos-index.html>

⁹<http://universaldependencies.github.io/docs/format.html>

TUT

USD

Core dependents of clausal predicates

VERB-SUBJ VERB-OBJ VERB-INDOBJ VERB-OBJ/VERB-SUBJ VERB-PREDCOMPL+OBJ	<i>nsubj, csubj dobj, ccomp iobj nsubjpass, csubjpass xcomp</i>
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Non-core dependents of clausal predicates

ADVB-RMOD ADVB-RMOD-NEG VERB+FIN-RMOD NOUN-RMOD NOUN-RMOD-TIME	<i>advmod neg advcl nmod tmod*</i>
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Special clausal dependents

NOUN-APPOSITION-VOCATIVE VERB-EXPLETIVE/VERB-SUBJ AUX+TENSE, AUX+PROGRESSIVE, VERB+MODAL-INDCOMPL AUX+PASSIVE VERB-PREDCOMPL+SUBJ CONJ-ARG END, SEPARATOR	<i>vocative expl aux auxpass cop mark punct</i>
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Noun dependents

ADJC(...)-RMOD DET+DEF-ARG DET+INDEF-ARG DET+QUANTIF-ARG PDET-RMOD NOUN-RMOD, NOUN-OBJ, NOUN-SUBJ NUM-RMOD VERB-RMOD+RELCL (...)APPOSITION(...)	<i>amod det, poss* det neg, nummod, det predet* nmod nummod relcl* appos</i>
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Case markers

PREP-RMOD	<i>case</i>
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Compounding and unanalyzed

CONTIN CONTIN+LOCUT CONTIN+DENOM, NOUN-APPOSITION-DENOM PARTICLE	<i>goeswith mwe, compound, name name prt*</i>
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Coordination

COORD(...) COORD2ND() COORDANTEC(...)	<i>cc conj, cc preconj*</i>
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Loose joining relations

NUM-RMOD-LISTPOS VERB-EXTRAOBJ, VERB-EXTRASUBJ	<i>list dislocated</i>
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Other

TOP(...) DEPENDENT, VISITOR	<i>root dep</i>
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Figure 3: Mapping scheme of (the more relevant) TUT relations onto USD. USD relations marked with a * represent all those English-specific labels for which a direct counterpart in the TUT format already exists.

- conditions with `featuretype = mor` require the presence of a particular morphological feature in the Part of Speech of the X element of the TUT relation
 Ex.: `DET+DEF-ARG, det (Gmor: ART DEF)` is the mapping function that falls in the R-swapped category described above, and that specifies that the TUT relation for definite determiners `DET+DEF-ARG` should be renamed as `det` if the governor of the TUT relation satisfies the morphological condition (`mor`) of being a definite article `ART DEF`.
- conditions with `featuretype = syn` require the presence or absence (indicated by + or -) of a particular syntactic structure associated with the X element of the TUT relation;
 Ex.: `VERB-INDOBJ, nmod (Gsyn + DEP& PREP)` is the mapping function that falls in the R-renamed category, and that specifies that the TUT relation for indirect objects `VERB-INDOBJ` must be renamed as `nmod` when the given node has a dependent (`DEP`) which is a preposition (`PREP`).

If a rule has more than one condition, this will be of the form:

```
TUTrelation,SDrelation(Xmor:condition;Xsyn+/-:condition).
```

5 Discussion

This section attempts to illustrate some of the relevant aspects that involved this conversion project.

As mentioned above, in this first stage of development of our work, we decided to fully adhere to the USD annotation principles and label set, in order to comply with the standard, and, at the same time, to assess its actual applicability to the parallel texts in ParTUT. However, a number of issues raised from the conversion, as we tested it on the texts of the collection. These aspects mostly had to do with the specific features of the two formats, and with the theoretical as well as technical reasons that lie behind their conception, rather than the differences between the language pairs involved. The observations emerged both from the design of the conversion model and the actual results obtained with the automatic process can be basically reduced to three main issues, that we will attempt to examine in this section; they regard: the differences in annotation granularity, the uniformity in the parallel annotation, and the actual coverage, using the current label set and representation scheme, of the linguistic phenomena encountered in the collection.

Different granularities: pros and cons of both formats As far as the difference in annotation and label granularity is concerned, with its set of 11 *morphoSyntactic* and 27 *functionalSyntactic* features can be combined together, the TUT format has a far richer scheme compared to the one adopted in USD (where the taxonomy includes an overall amount of 43 relations). This intuitively let one assume

that conversion from finer- to coarse-grained labels would be more straightforward. However, the rationale behind these differences lies namely on the different principles and linguistic layers that are meant to be described, such as the predicate-argument structure in the TUT representation format. Let us consider, for example, the case of predicative modifiers. TUT introduces a distinction between arguments and adjuncts that, because of its subtlety, has been intentionally removed in SD and USD. This results in the absence of a proper counterpart for the TUT relation used to express the predicative modifier (RMODPRED), which has then been considered as a simple modifier (either nominal, adjectival or clausal) according to the USD scheme.

On the other hand, while in USD compounding is distinguished from phrasal modification by using a specific label (that is namely *compound*), such distinction is not drawn in TUT, where they are generically defined as modifiers (NOUN-RMOD or NUM-RMOD, depending on whether they include nouns or numerals). As a result, it is quite impossible to keep this distinction during the automatic conversion, and a manual post-editing step is necessarily required in those cases.

Uniformity in parallel annotation One of the advantages of a "universal" representation scheme, as claimed by [4], is "*the parallelism between different constructions across and within languages*" (p.3). In fact, besides the release of a *parallel* treebank into a widely-recognized format that enables its portability, the second main goal that motivated this conversion is the exploitation of the USD representation for translation purposes and in the ongoing development of a syntactic alignment system that could overcome, benefitting from the dependency-based annotation, the problems raised by the so-called *translation shifts* [3, 13]. We report therefore some qualitative observations about the capacity of USD for preserving a higher degree of parallelism under a structural perspective and better serving the purposes of an automatic alignment system with respect to TUT. We considered a small sample consisting of 20 sentences from each language section and annotated in USD, taking into account two main criteria: *i*) all the sentences must have a 1:1 correspondence, this means that each subset of the sample is a triple containing the same sentence in the English, French and Italian version respectively; and *ii*) they must contain at least one example of translation shifts (see [13]). In line with the *lexicalist* approach adopted for the USD design, whereby grammatical relations should hold between content words, in our observations on the sample data, we considered the latter only and defined the set of dependency edges that link them in a sentence as the *core* structure of that sentence. We thus compared each annotated triple, and attempted to determine the frequency of the following cases: *i*) same core structure, i.e. content words are linked with the same edges and relations in each sentence of the triple, as the example in Figure 4 (which also highlights an important difference with respect to TUT as regards the head-selection criteria); *ii*) similar core structure, i.e. content words are linked with the same edges in each sentence of the triple, but with (either partially or completely) different relations

(see Figure 5); *iii*) different structures.

Figure 4: An example of same core structures in USD (upper part), despite the presence of a translation shift from nominal (English version) to prepositional modification (French and Italian counterparts). Because of the differences in the original conception of the representation format, TUT annotation (lower part) offers a divergent version of the example proposed that does not preserve this uniformity .

For the cases *i* and *ii*, we also verified whether such conditions occur in only two out of three sentences of the triple. What emerged from this comparison is that most of the sentence triples had the same core structure (around 60%), and less than 17% had different structures. This seems to confirm the advantage of the USD scheme, with respect to TUT (as also shown in Figure 4).

Coverage of label set and representation conventions As regards this aspect, the coarser granularity of relations offered by the USD scheme makes it possible their applicability to a wide range of linguistic phenomena. This allows us, for the time being, to exploit the resource without the need to enrich the taxonomy with new labels, and to stick to the original intention, which is to remain faithful to the proposed standard. It should also be added that we used for Italian and French as well a large part of those relation labels that in the scheme proposed in the official documentation are referred to as English-specific. This sub-set of relations is easily identified in Table 3 as marked with an asterisk (*). Furthermore, except for *prt* (the label expressing particles in phrasal verbs), that is used in ParTUT for English only, all the remaining relations listed in the table can be applied to all the three languages of the treebank.

Beyond the observations reported above, however, we detected that the USD scheme offers a limited coverage for what concerns many, albeit rare, phenomena (which is an aspect that has also been observed in [9]). In particular we did not find in USD the means to deal with comparative structures, which often occur in a rich repertory of variants especially in Italian and French. Also the representation

Figure 5: Example of similar core structures in the presence of a shift in the morpho-syntactic category of the root modifier (that is verb in the English and Italian example and noun in the French version).

of various types of relative clauses have been kept underspecified in the current version of ParTUT in USD format.

This motivates our plans for the future advancement of this work, where we intend to design and apply more adequate representation of a larger variety of linguistic phenomena, following the hints of [9] and benefitting from the richness of the source format, in particular the explicit annotation of null elements.

6 Conclusion and future work

In this paper we presented an ongoing work on the conversion of a parallel treebank into the Universal Stanford Dependencies. The main goal of this conversion project is the release of a treebank that is not only annotated according to the principles of a scheme that currently represents a *de facto* standard in treebank design, but also contains parallel texts that, benefiting from a uniform annotation across the different languages, can then be exploited for practical NLP tasks, such as multilingual parsing and Machine Translation.

The next steps are the full release of the treebank and its use as a test of the alignment approach described in [14].

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